

Scelotes anguinus

Algoa Dwarf Burrowing Skink

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Reptile

Size: 10-20 cm (total body length)

Distribution:

Endemic to South Africa, Algoa Basin in Eastern Cape.

Importance:

It is a key model species in the *Scelotes* genus for studying limbless development (forelimb digits = 0; hindlimb digits = 0) and vertebrate genomic evolution. Its restricted distribution also makes it valuable for biogeographic and molecular ecology studies.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 28.82 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 2.93 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 1.53 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 89.4% [Single: 87.5%, Duplicated: 2.0%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 111.52 kilobases

Contig number: 38 837

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